

Discourses on Research Freedom in the Academic Study of Religion. An Overview

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1 Introduction

While there has been a lot of scholarship on the question of religious freedom, less attention has been paid to conceptual problems surrounding academic freedom in the study of religion. My purpose is to introduce the issue. I neither claim to be exhaustive, nor aspire to a full or in-depth treatment of themes and theorists introduced. Instead, this study seeks to break ground by providing an overview. This essay brings together questions, arguments, and narratives in the framework of which the issue has been addressed and expressed. It adopts the approach of 'discursive research', and seeks to trace the production of the meaning of 'freedom' that is legitimated and shared in the Academic Study of Religion.

I shall give a breakdown of this process of meaning-production along the following lines: the authority, the rights, and the impartiality of science particularly with regard to both the concept of '(Religious)Value-Free' and the program of the 'academic freedom from religion'. Besides I describe a counternarrative based on what I may call 'Non-Religious-Value'-Free and the academic program of the 'autonomy of religion' (emancipation from politics, economy, etc.). Eventually, I acknowledge a complementarity between the two narratives, as well as between the notions of facts-given and god/church-given freedom.

The central takeaway of the essay is the recognition of a binary opposition between the senses of freedom along these lines, which has evolved through mutual criticism within a two-fold system. It is a system of free inquiry which strikes me as having increased polarization, reduced the set of options and achieved a status quo. Most of this essay deals with the fallacy of freedom in the Academic Study of Religion.

2 Authority and Freedom of Science

As the goal of this essay is to trace the making of the meaning of freedom in the Academic Study of Religion, it goes back to the beginnings of this discipline and starts the investigation with some of its earliest representatives.

The French free-thinker Ernest Renan, in the preface to his *Études d'histoire religieuse*, declares that “[...] all that science asks for is freedom” (1857: xxiv).

This radical ‘nothing more’-claim seems to be generally held. Only a couple of decades later, Alfred Loisy stated that the “science of religions” cannot be established until a process which subjects to “free inquiry” is implemented, and made this instruction the “only law” to be followed (1909: 5). He included such a declaration in the inaugural speech to the lectures delivered at the Collège de France in 1909, in his capacity as a representative of the European Catholic Modernist movement, in the aftermath of his excommunication *vitandus*. However, even if he championed freedom, he himself phrased its limitations and contradictions: “Man is not free to think whatever he pleases,”; he also framed the issue in the following manner: “No man [...] has the right to think against the truth” (Loisy 1919: 145–146). He found it to be far more appropriate in scientific research to speak about the “obligation of disciplining one’s intellect to search for the truth” than about freedom (1919: 155).

A similar idea of obligation in scientific research – as opposed to absolute freedom – emerged in the intellectual environment of the Dutch Reformed Church, as well. Cornelis Petrus Tiele, when elaborating on history proper (i.e. as a discipline), held that historians may address the “description of history” without considering the underlying law: they are “free to do so” (Tiele 1897: 215). But when we come to a scholarly approach to history, freedom shall not apply: we should both look at human history as a history ruled by laws, and explain its development: “we must do so whether we please or not”, according to Tiele, “because it is the task and the duty of science” (1897: 215). He advocated that the latter approach is necessary for the “science of religion”, which means that a scholar is not free to leave the underlying laws of history out of consideration in research.

This late nineteenth- and early twentieth century set of examples consists of responses of European representatives to the call of a liberal Christian clergy for scientific studies of religion. It illustrates different impacts and reactions: estrangement (Renan, initially trained in Catholic seminaries), expulsion (Loisy), or reform from within (Tiele, Remonstrant pastor). This eclectic mix of sources and quotations coming from different frameworks, even if without unpacking the specific concerns of those frameworks, gives a sketch and show the extent of the pattern of the authority of science in the views of religious or academic freedom among scholars.

The twentieth century brought similar developments in non-church affiliated organizations. While concentrating on establishing some requirements for the scientific study of religion, the question of freedom was overshadowed. During a congress of the member-organization of the CIPSH/ UNESCO, the International Association for the History of Religions in Marburg, in 1960, there was a discussion concerning the necessity or defense of a scientific method. Some members found it essential to lay down certain basic assumptions which are to be presupposed for the very possibility of a scientific study of religions. In the resulting statement, the key issue is 'truth'. The common ground in which scholars of religions could meet is their willingness to replace "transcendent" by "historical truth", in a way that implies unquestionability: "the awareness of the numinous or the experience of transcendence are – whatever else they may be – *undoubtedly* empirical facts" (Schimmel 1960: 236–237). It is remarkable that the issue of freedom did not surface in the statement explicitly in a way that would have demanded the scholars' full attention.

Two decades later, it could still be observed that in the subsequent discussions of non-church-affiliated circles, the 'freedom of research' was hardly the chief consideration. Far more critical issues appeared to be decisive. Such was Donald Wiebe's perspective: "as any other scientific enterprise [...] the academic study of religion [...] is subject first and foremost to 'the authority of facts'" (1988: 407). This approach may be paralleled to the arguments of the

“obligation” to search for the truth and the scientific “task and [...] duty” to consider laws of history, elaborated on already by the above-mentioned early scholars coming from a liberal Christian background (Loisy 1919: 155; Tiele 1897: 215). It is puzzling to notice that notwithstanding their different approaches, they all emphasize more the submissive than the free character of science. Furthermore, it is remarkable that when Wiebe expressed worries concerning the “very notion of science” later on, saying that it was “under attack”, the justification was that the “notion of science as an epistemological privileged type of knowledge is today criticized” (Wiebe 2003: 168), and not that freedom of research is being endangered.

Such a claim in defense of an epistemologically privileged/dominant science is not unanimously accepted, notably by Kocku von Stuckrad who is committed to a ‘discursive’ / Foucauldian approach to the study of religion. According to him “the scholar is also an author whose narrative account does not provide a privileged access to truth” (2013: 10). He highlights that where the construction of facts that starts up scientific inquiries or, in other words, the fact-making process (social legitimation of meanings which are made available, shared, self-evident, and objectified) is negated, there is a misunderstanding of the scientific method (von Stuckrad 2013).

What is more, even Wiebe who welcomes the authority of science opposes the idea of ‘enslavement’ to a “cult of facts”, or “‘privileged access’ for some to the data” (1988: 411), and stands at least for public knowledge, which is inter-subjectively available for scrutiny. But, no matter how advanced is the attempt to reconcile authority and freedom, by adding auxiliary assumptions, the issue of a hardline knowledge which denies the right to think against the truth or facts remains in the debate, just as long as it is asserted within non-church-affiliated or church-affiliated organizations.

I do not seek to give more than a few remarks which may help to get my point across, in so far as the question of freedom of research seems to be set against the background of a set of premises about scientific knowledge which make this question far less essential, if not meaningless, or, at best, barely

adequate. An objection to this could be that a large number of studies speak wholeheartedly in favor of the validity of freedom of research and not one rejects it – though seemingly obvious, yet not a compelling argument.

An ultimate point to be mentioned here, with reference to the issue of authority and freedom, is that of those who see the task of the Academic Study of Religion in opposing authority, considering Thomas Kuhn's *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962) as a point of reference. The reason behind this is that the discipline is meant to address anomalies and it may have a destabilizing effect, taking into account the issue as it is framed: the “shift from a religious to a scientific regime of truth” entails “innovation, discovery, challenges to authority and to tradition,”; “all came to be positively valorized” (Lincoln 2012: 51–52). Kippenberg even claims that the discipline came into being as “a study inspired not by faith but by doubt” (2002: 68). This turns the early history of the scientific study of religion into a narrative that reads like a chapter in the modern history of the “rise of liberty” – which means a “loss of certainty” (Kippenberg 2002: 68).

3 Abuse of Right or Weak Right

Scholars of religions posed questions about what claim they can make to scientific authority, and the rights this authority grants them. In other words, if a scholar defines a religion or a set of beliefs, in what field is his definition valid – can it go beyond science and claim validity for/over the religious subjects? Can the right of (self-)definition be taken away from the religious subject and be given to the scholar? It has been discussed, for example, if to “define” Hinduism means “to deny the Hindu his right to the freedom and integrity of his faith”¹ i.e. his right to define his own faith. Because as soon as scholars “define”, as a result, they “set limits”; and with regard to “any limitations that

¹ More will need to be said about Smith's call for the word “faith” to replace “religion” and to apply it to Hinduism, which some contemporary scholars might question (Asad 2001: 207–208 about Smith's clinging to a latent essentialism, despite his antiessentialist instinct). In this essay, I shall not dwell on that matter which would require to be investigated separately.

our intellects may attempt to impose upon [...] human history” (Smith W. 1964: 131), it shall be clear in which cases this limitation can be applied, or to what degree it is acceptable.

“[E]mphasis” is always placed on the need to “resist encroachments on academic freedom of inquiry”. It is equally stressed, however, “that academics have no right to encroach on the freedom of belief of non-academics”. That is to say that “our freedom to re-describe others” should be “matched by their freedom [...] to decide [...] whether] to allow those re-descriptions to replace the self-description they already have” (Edwards 1994: 181).

Jonathan Z. Smith asks whether the re-description of religious canon for the purpose of scholarly generalization and comparison results in the “removal of all rights to interpretation from the native” (1988: 43), in a few remarkable lines which turn out to be one of the all-time favorite quotations from his writings. Historians of religion who are concerned with the “archaic” argue in favor of such a “removal”, justifying it with the theory according to which the more primitive a religious subject is, the less ability of interpretation may be expected from him. This claim of “uninterpreted” archaic data has “given historians of religion license for ultimate acts of imperialism”, since it has suggested the “arrogation of all such rights [to interpretation] to themselves” (Smith 1988: 43). Smith suggested sticking with an approach grounded in expository discourses instead and redirecting attention in such instances, the result of which would be that “historians of religion will not lose their freedom to study [...] objects of religious concern, but that they will take as a prime interpretative and comparative task the understanding of the surrender of that freedom by the communities they study” (Smith 1988: 44).

The “challenge to achieve reciprocity” should be accepted as an act of “mutual modulation, within the context of comparison” (Smith 1988: 36, 52). A similar issue has been raised from the angle of discourse analysis, with respect to “the freedom of the parties involved to choose the terms under which each one wants to envisage reality; otherwise” – Jean Jacques Waardenburg went on – “the discussion itself would lose its meaning and could be replaced by a

solution of power, involving oppression” (1978: 179).

The dangers of unwarranted extension of the so-called “religious freedom” and “religious rights” may exceed the dangers which are cited as grounds for advocating such an extension. According to Russell T. McCutcheon, the risks inherent in overlooking “the manner in which these so-called freedoms have been defined, to whose benefit their definition contributes” stand undiminished. For, by “focusing only on how to extend these [religious] freedoms [...], as if ‘worship’ exhausted the sorts of behaviors that can conceivably fall under ‘the inherent right to do’ [...], one leaves unidentified the practical, historical constraints on forms of doing and ways of organizing” (2003: 277). That may result in “failing to understand ‘freedom’ not to be an absolute, ahistoric value but part of a discourse shaped by a larger grammar of conformity and control” (2003: 278). The same underlying concern of this risk informs McCutcheon’s writing a decade later, too: If “we [...] as scholars” are not “free to move beyond participants’ use of folk taxonomies and self-definitions”, then “uncritically reproducing – instead of studying – local classification systems” (that is “the mechanisms by which identities are created and contested”) will “lead us to normalizing and thus legitimizing participant distinctions and the interests that drive (or once drove) them” (McCutcheon 2013: 12–13).

Another leading approach to the study of religion is that free inquiry must and cannot but weaken its own rights, and lower its obligations, in order to avoid the above-mentioned ‘solution of power’ or ‘imperialism’ and the abuses which may follow. As examples to this approach, we might turn back to the first scholars of the field, visited earlier. Interestingly, the free-thinker Ernest Renan saw a paradox and exhorted to keep it in play. He elaborated on the concept of a “weak right [*faible droit*]” of science (1857: xxi), though not out of reverence due to any kind of religious observance. Even for the excommunicated Catholic Alfred Loisy, to whom I referred earlier with regard to the “only law”-theory (§ 1), churches were “free to require that their members shut their eyes to any outcome of critical inquiry, however well-founded it may be, should it unsettle their traditional view of theology” and “should” the churches

“still manage to think that they have the right to do so, and that it is their real interest” (1919: 156). It is remarkable that he should uphold this view a decade after his excommunication.

Staying with the pioneers, we may find that Friedrich Max Müller also treated the issue of religious rights, extending the question from the traditional view of theology of a given church to any kind of dogmatic mindset, but arriving at a different approach. In his speech *On Freedom* delivered in Birmingham, he did “not think of religious dogma only [...] but rather of [...] dogmatic state of mind”; or, as he called it, “dead knowledge” (1881: 508–509). In this regard, the Science of Religion is not supposed to grant rights. Rather it endorses a fight against conformity. The word “self-government”, which runs throughout his essay *On Freedom*, strikes as a key issue, as well as the phrase “the struggle of all against all” (Max Müller 1881: 489). These citations are meant to reflect on the history of the field as far as “freedom” is concerned. In these cases, we observe the idea that freedom is a matter of independence. I turn now to a more detailed examination of this negative way to define what freedom is by referring to what it should not conform to.

4 (Religious) Value-Free

A negative criterion of freedom of research, often called ‘Value-Free’, occasionally referred to with Weber’s concept *Wertfreiheit*, became standard in the Academic Study of Religion. It is a standard which is largely recognized as presenting weakness and strengths. On the one hand, when the focus given to the larger question of free inquiry is fastened on the smaller, allegedly more fundamental idea of ‘free of value’ (i.e. value-free inquiry), there occurs a disproportionate narrowing down. On the other hand, it is my personal impression, based on my 20-year experience in the field, that it is perhaps the strongest criterion upon which this field has been built, in the sense that it has always been and still seems to me the most capable of overcoming criticism. This is the criterion that invites the most effort on both sides: of those who want to rescue this criterion from refutation, as well as those who wish to get rid of it.

The 'Value-Free' criterion could not be more regularly belittled. Many critics have argued that the 'Value Free' principle in science is a farce, and that we must stop the "illusion" which would mislead us under the guise of fairness (Stausberg & Engler 2011: xxi). A "comedy of innocence" happens to be performed in a poor attempt at neutrality. Many scholars take the attitude that they can distance themselves from the values of their own culture, just by putting its key-words, e.g. religion, "in inverted commas" (Stausberg 2010a: 355). So it was apparently necessary to state once again that it is a common notion today that there is no "view from nowhere" (von Stuckrad 2003: 259). The response to the 'Value-Free' issue has been overactive enough to be considered just as valuable as "flogging a dead horse" (Werblowsky 1975: 154). It has resulted in a subjectivist reaction against the ideal of objectivity/impartiality, and appeared to go too far in running the advocacy of a 'free of value'-cause down in every respect. Such a reaction would be just a hyperbole with a dose of fraud, or so it was assumed. This assumption has been put into several practical forms, easy to handle, like the following sarcastic sentence: "well, now I am going to be subjective with a vengeance!" (Werblowsky 1987: 55), or other expressions of similar wording that might have some effect in the way of derisive refutation.

As a justification for the essentiality of being Value-free, it has been emphasized that the Churches or religions had exploited the Academic Study of Religion to promote their values and interests, as it were, in service of ideological or theological agendas. Such a defense of Value-free requested the scientific approach "to free itself" from the theological-ideological agendas (Wiebe 2006: 691), and eventually not to feel exempt from the obligations of a pure i.e. objective, neutral, unbiased, cognitive knowledge/truth. The academic community has been urged to stick with a "Value-Free Study of Religion" (Wiebe 2019: 238–255). These arguments give us a glimpse of the way in which freedom of research was – and still is – largely designed to answer that demand of being free of religious or ideological value, failing which would mean that "science is destroyed" (Wiebe 1988: 407, 412).

Against this whole defense, objections were brought forward in holding that its appeal to every academic student of religion to hold fast to a “value-free science”, that is “objectivity”, twists freedom into power. The requirement to comply with a ‘Value-Free’ approach seemed to be far more a matter of authority of scholarship (which “authorized” a “naturalistic” approach to objects of inquiry given by nature regardless of cultures); and privilege (“the privileging of what has traditionally been conceived of as the neutral and value-free space of the scholar [...] over against the value-laden reflections”) (McCutcheon 1997: 193, 81). A further argument was drawn from this, that “critique is greatly weakened when” it “relies on a positivist understanding of [...] value-free knowledge” (1997: 97), since such positivist master narrative of objectivity and freedom would allow authority and privileges of science to remain unidentified and unexposed.

One particular form of the objections which have been made e.g. by Timothy Fitzgerald was that what we get used to calling “Value-Free” is a rather value-laden label designating the secular sphere of objective facts (2000: 8). Furthermore, what is to be understood by clearing a cognitive space for scientific knowledge puts us in a position to think of another separate sphere of knowledge, namely the ‘sacred’. These remarks were intended to suggest that this binary classification (value-free/having a religious value) is a modern Western self-construction, presented as evident and universal. It has to be “legitimated as part of the real world [...] that all societies are conceived as evolving toward”, and “to which all cultures [...] should conform” (Fitzgerald 2000: 6–8). It is suggested then that Value-Free spells domination, i.e. the exportation of a Western value and its global acceptance under conditions which reduce any opposition to alternatives within the Western status quo. As the essay addresses the question of colonialism, it must at least refer to some of the more influential post-colonial critics. I shall confine myself to mentioning only a few references which could help to ground my examination within arguments in the field. According to Charles H. Long, Western scientific objectivity reflects “an ideological bias” using “the neutrality of distancing

in time and space” to prevent a true situation of contact (1986: 65, 71), which reads to me as a cultural segregation. Talal Asad criticized the “scientific definition of anthropology as a disinterested (objective, value-free) study of ‘other cultures’” inasmuch it makes the contact with non-Europeans “safe”, “one sided and provisional” (1973: 17–18).

5 Post-Religion Studies and the Academic Freedom from Religion

In the last decades, a number of attempts have been made to sustain that the concept of ‘religion’ is characteristic of an “explicit or implicit theological domination”. The question of freedom is stated as being a question of whether a scholar, adopting a sociological or anthropological critical perspective, “progressively freed him or herself” from this concept for it is analytically irrelevant (Fitzgerald 2000: 8). We are urged to avoid uncritically applying it and exporting it in the study of cultures wherein this word is an alien, imposed, and distorting Western construct. Students of religion are expected to look inward, by examining their own attitude toward the ideology of Religious Studies, which is a system capable of mistaking “cognitive imperialism”, serving the interests of Western ideology, for global inclusive enlargement of religion (Fitzgerald 2000: 13). They must come to the conclusion that this ideology has been at the best only a form of “liberal ecumenical Christian theology” to date (Fitzgerald 2000). This theory may be differently worded, thus: Religious Studies achieve a manipulation of freedom, i.e. it satisfies the desire of freedom of religions it actually has first created as a human need. It allows the preservation of a “European universalism” in the language of religious pluralism, by reframing colonialist views in terms of freedom of religions (with reference to Masuzawa 2005). This may also be expressed by saying that Western knowledge and power have authorized forms of history-making, including the history of religions, that is the European construction of religion as an anthropological category (Asad 1993).

A change was envisioned in the details of a renewed process of elimination / demise of religion. To designate this process of “stop talking about ‘religion’”,

the phrase “academic freedom from ‘religion’” seemed better fitting in the view of Matthew Day (2010: 274–275). It is expressive of what might be called “the post-religion study of religion” (Stausberg 2010: 232–233). The discourse on an “outsider, detached, scientific approach to religion” which counts as freedom is illustrated by this instance in the sense that we are told: science “works to free itself from religio-theological [...] and all other similar agendas in an attempt to obtain such disinterested [neutral / objective; i.e. non-religious] knowledge about religion” (Wiebe 2014: 20; 2006: 691).

One might dispute the fairness of statements on “the re-formulation of the problem of religion”, which make a mockery of the progress made in what was liable to be labeled “religionless religion”, saying that it is a “freak oddity”, put bluntly by Werblowsky (1975: 156). In one case which seems unfair to me, and which I would like to mention because there are certain controversial aspects associated with it, all the weight of the ridicule falls upon the Death-of-God Theology (Dietrich Bonhoeffer’s concept of “religionless Christianity” precisely [Pugh 2008]), the only candidate that is dubbed ineligible to serve the secularization of religion, and, at the same time, which is required to give up on its challenges. Oddly enough, according to Werblowsky, no way could the “student of comparative religion” who “operates, by definition, from an archimedic point outside religion” (1975: 152), have been equally grotesque, even if his/her ‘outside religion’-approach was similar to the ‘religionless’-approach, and even if the two freedoms from religion have overlapped at some point. In my view, similarities could be possibly seen if we described them like this, namely speaking of two ‘exit doors’ from religion opened by academic outsiders or religious insiders, from without or within.

As far as the issue of freedom is concerned, one main objection has been suggested to the Post-Religion scholars. According to Michael Stausberg, even if we had admitted their “partly justified and partly exaggerated accusations of ethnocentric, (neo)colonial and imperialist implications” of the category of religion in the academic studies of non-Western cultures, their argument, that is – the way I see it – “there can be no free science if it is a science of religion”,

would still be inconclusive. We certainly cannot underplay the dilemma faced by a free science based on a Western globalizing pattern. Neither can we be blind to the criticism directed at the assumed *sui-generis* nature of this pattern (the assumption that religion is unique in kind, and has a transcendent and universal essence). Nevertheless, any discussion of this subject, should at least sustain the following objection, which I share, that “a kind of reverse-*sui-generis* rhetoric” is activated, which runs counter to the “first-order *sui-generis*” (Stausberg 2010a: 364–365). This “second order reverse *sui generis* approach” leads to the upside-down idea of an un-universal, un-cross-cultural concept which is expected to give rise to an unprecedented obligation to get free of it in the academic studies, “as if it were an inherently more problematic concept than others”, such as ‘politics’, ‘economy’, and so on and so forth, “indeed an anomalous one” (Stausberg 2010a: 365).

The following is to be considered too. Many times had the defenders of the first-order *sui generis* discourse, such as Raffaele Pettazzoni, based their defense not merely on the ground that religion is free, and no history can be freed from it, but also on the ground that history is free, and not a single “aspect [it.: *carattere*]” e.g. political, social, religious and so on, can be “elevated to a paradigm for the study of [the whole] history” (Pettazzoni 1924: 11–12). It was called “law of development / unfolding [*svolgimento*]” which, according to the early twentieth-century Italian Historicism, “means freedom” (1924: 19–20), in the sense that anything in the history is *sui generis*, and there is not just one ruling “religion-prototype [*religione-tipo*]” (1924: 20): even the most pervasive, i.e. the type of religion distinct from “social life”, which started to develop lately, is seemingly universal simply because monotheisms made it to be so by seeking to impose it on a large scale (1924: 25–26). Without entering at length into an examination of the historicist positions (for instance, the paradox historicists may run into, when they adhere to the theory that freedom must be explained by considering the rules of History), I restrict myself to saying that, at least in this case, the first-order *sui generis* discourse does not raise a religious issue for this discourse does not affect only religion, but also the meaning of History.

In the Nineties, the historicist School of Rome attempted to bring the debate on the 'academic freedom from religion' to an end. They founded their objection on the ground of contradiction. Should the efforts to depart, or retract our cultural views, i.e. to get rid of the category of religion in historical inquiry, ever prove successful, we "should give away our entire culture", as well as all "the issues that it has the capacity to raise" (Sabbatucci 2000: 107), not excluding the 'Religion-Free' issue. Without the Academic Study of Religion, the criticism that results could not possibly have been obtained, or would definitely be discontinued and endangered. The argument is that the freedom from religion in comparative studies is paradoxically self-repressive of the very concept which enables comparison and, at the same time, lays the basis for its criticism. This argument is based on the fact that we must deal with history as it is, and not as it might be, had our culture been different. Had we been able to avoid seeing other cultures *sub specie religionis*, we certainly would not have ascribed to them the same functions religion substantially performs with us; but maybe we would not have ascribed to them any function at all.

I am unwilling to admit that the 'academic freedom from religion' is an accessory to repression in the sense that it discredits and rejects the category which can guide to the understanding of our established culture in its repressive structure; to the extent that is it repressive. But I do believe that the question should stay with us in the debate. The question remains whether the category of religion still needs to be questioned as applying to comparative studies. In that regard, I am confident that the Academic Study of Religion can be something more than calling the bluff of religion as a human value. Whether or not, or to what extent quitting criticism of religion all at once, and putting an end to disturbing the accepted uses of this word as a category, would be of advantage to free inquiry, is, in my view, by no means clear.

Further shortcomings on the subject of Post-religion as well as Post-theological studies tended to be subsumed in the question of the fallout of free inquiry. Tomáš Bubík has argued that the liberation of science these two fields have worked for, namely the freedom from theological influence, has contributed

to the undermining of the liberalization of theology, since it has hindered the “reverse influence” which science may exercise on theological studies and religious knowledge (at least toward increasing their “ability to deal with plurality”, challenging “the concept of ‘one truth’”, and to “secularize”: see Bubík 2016: 263–264). A side- and adverse effect was triggered, the result of which feeds the type of freedom that Post-theological studies wish for, but eventually sets off a vicious circle which increases restrictions which legitimize estrangement. The question whether at some point this vicious circle might be broken, and interferences allowed, and even recommended, became ripe for discussion in Central Europe in the last three decades; but also, as far as the Czech case-study is concerned, since the political transformation after 1948, a dialogical and yet ambivalent ‘reverse influence’ took place (Bubík 2015: 29–41).

The academic freedom from theology has been questioned on different historical grounds. From the Japanese standpoint, it became rather an obsessive time-honored Euro-Western mission that which tried “to detach” the studies of religion/s “from theology” (Fujiwara 2020: 58). “Ironically” – it has been said – such a model of freedom forces criticism into repetitive loops which draw it away beyond the reach of the new challenges of academic freedom, since this model is “overdetermined by” its “relationships with theology” (Fujiwara 2020: 58). As a consequence, it can “isolate” our studies from the overarching discussions on free scientific research now taking place internationally, concerning, for instance, how governmental funding can influence or interfere with academic research programs if it is granted to “economically profitable applied studies”, and to what measure “budget cuts” serve “as a means of stronger state control” (Fujiwara 2020: 55, 58).

With regard to the limits of “Western liberalism”, and if we need to get rid of it somehow, it is pertinent to add a further and complementary item. It was discussed by a working group set up in 1988 at a meeting of the International Association for the History of Religions to explore possibilities for scholarly cooperation between Muslim and Non-Muslim scholars. What struck the board as “handicapping” the adoption of the discipline was that “Western liberalism”

was seen by “many Muslims” as an implied norm and value of Religious Studies, which, therefore, seemed to them “as being imported from the West”. For this reason – I read from the report – “such studies are distrusted” (Antes [et al.] 1989: 150–151).

6 God/Church-Given Freedom and ‘Non-Religious Value’-Free

“[T]he history of religions enterprise could be viewed [...] from either angle, as furthering either the cause of value-free science (if such exists) or of liberal Christianity [...]” (Sharpe 2016: 101). I quote from a commonly accepted and recently reprinted text on the early history of the Academic Study of Religion. It is expressive of the building up of a two-fold concept of freedom within a cohesive system which, notably since the first international congress for the study of the History of Religions (Paris, 1900), perpetuates both the opposition and the coexistence between two divergent tendencies. “This same ambiguity [of the concept of freedom]” – the text went on to state – “persisted in the post-war years” (Sharpe 2016: 101).

I have discussed the cause of value-free science in § 5 and § 6. A few references may suffice now to provide some insight into liberal Christianity’s concept of God/Church-given freedom and its trends, as well as some evidence of its input in the long run. In 1946, Gerardus van der Leeuw referred to “freedom, [and] independence of science” as being “divine values [...] given to us [...] as [...] an order to execute” (1954: 15), while publicly confessing that he never “felt the need to forget” that he was a “theologian” (1954: 13). The text of this “scientific confession” was published in the first issue of the flagship journal of the *iahr* (van der Leeuw 1954). In 1968, the same journal published another article of a similar character, implying that free inquiry in scientific research is a theological concept and including Biblical references, such as *2 Corinthians* 3:17 (“[...] where the Spirit of the Lord is, there is liberty”) (Clavier 1968: 118). Robert Charles Zaehner presented his studies on comparative religion with an oxymoron, that he had deliberately and “freely accepted the ‘bondage’ of the Catholic Church”, i.e. its Christocentric pattern (Zaehner 1970: 16).

Joachim Wach deserves a more extended notice. He refers to the issue of the self-directing freedom of religion, commonly referred to as the issue of the “autonomy of religion” in scientific research, as we can read in the following: “[T]he history of religions”, so the argument runs, “has encountered from the very beginning” difficulties “in its struggle to be free from [external] domination [...] of politics and dogma”; it “has been forced, as hardly any other discipline has, to support and serve now this, now that establishment, cause, or movement” (Wach 1988: 11–12). The question of “servitude” is raised with respect to “the conditions for a science (*Wissenschaft*) of religions” to be met in order to be “truly free and unprejudiced”; conditions which, according to Wach, “were first created in the successful parrying of attacks against the autonomy of religion” (Wach 1988: 22). This call for the “Emancipation of the History of Religions” is motivated by the recognition that the “structure (*Gesetzlichkeit*) of religious life [...] is original, and thus in the end it cannot be comprehended from the point of view of [e.g.] philosophy [...] or ethics,” and so on (Wach 1988: 26). This stress laid on freedom from non-religious points of view would constitute a methodological prescription for academic studies.

I shall call this assumption the theory of ‘Non-Religious Value’-Free, using this expression to stress similarities with the theory of ‘(Religious) Value’-Free that would be as incorrect to overlook, as it is to overemphasize. No one who knows anything about the history of the Academic Study of Religion can make the mistake to mix the defense of Value-Free science with similar arguments phenomenologists gave as being relevant both to religious values and science, let alone the following. Van der Leeuw recommended acknowledging that religious values “are not conditioned by a particular point of view, but are values before God”, and are “concerned with what is eternal” (1963: 5). This insight suggests something along the lines of a ‘divine objectivity’.

7 Freedom Binarism

I am not here to stifle dissent against neither the ‘God/Church given’ (§ 7) nor the ‘(Religious) Value-Free’ theories of freedom (see § 5 and 6). Nor am

I ready to invite impartiality, by reproducing and re-activating the communicative structure and process of negotiation, called 'neutrality', that made the 'History of Religions' enterprise ambiguously practicable. My purpose is to de-construct the scholarly work of the 'freedom of research'-design. It is from this perspective that opposite discourses on freedom perpetuating an opposition within the same cohesive system seem complementary and capable to contain qualitative changes. I may term the outcome of this system the *status quo* of freedom in the Academic Study of Religion. To be sure, the 'History of Religions' enterprise tended to be polarized on the two conflicting concepts of freedom examined above, and framed in a symmetrical rhetoric of danger (intellectual bankruptcy, destruction of science, imperialism [see § 5]; or autonomy under attack, servitude [see § 7]). The "official picture of this academic field [...] of a group of [...] scholars working perilously close to two great dangers, reductionism and confessional theology" has been accurately described by Russell T. McCutcheon as "a picture with some resemblance to the Cold War-period portrait of Europe as helplessly situated between two threatening super-powers" (2003: 78). In such a binary system, in my view, the pluralism of freedom becomes deceptive, and self-determination limited by an academic narrative which instructs on how to think of liberation as coming from without (facts-given Value-Free) or from above (God-Given freedom). This essay is not concerned with the specific methodological implications of this complementarity for the study of religion. My point is to do the groundwork to simply observe the diverse problems confronting freedom. If anything, the theoretical pathway of this essay aspires to the acknowledgment of a kind of freedom which preserves the Academic Study of Religion within a pattern of criticism which integrates and governs oppositions. I report a reduction of options to a two-fold alternative underlying a master narrative. This is not a way of reconciling the theological concerns of insiders with secular studies of religions, and apparently incompatible understandings of the freedom of research which opposed each other. The other way around, I object to a system of freedom which absorbs alternatives, to a conflict based on a single binary

system that I may call ‘freedom binarism’ in the study of religion. Whether we may consider a theoretical space that exceeds this dichotomy may be the subject matter for another essay, and even more, a matter for post-Cold War studies of religion.

It would be hard to make a singular prescription for the whole field about who or what is constraining freedom, since the specific context for political or cultural constraints varies for scholars working in different national or institutional environments. The essay’s breadth does not permit to have an ambition to answer the questions mentioned in depth. But it does provide an overview of a disciplinary binary rule that could potentially – and actually did – call for restriction of options, and get some perspective on this condition. I do not intend to put forward anything like a full theory. I merely outline an idea and urge considerations on how this binarism might affect us as scholars with different subject-positions, and to what extent it weakens dissent.

If not binary freedom, then what? I wish to mention at least two cases which speak to the attempt made to overcome binarism: Max Müller’s appeal for a “struggle of all against all” in his speech *On Freedom*, with regard to the “dangers [...] which it is safer to face than to avoid” (1881: 489, 519); or the appeal for the “Babylonian confusion [...]” which, according to Werblowsky, is “a small price to pay for the scholar’s freedom” (1975: 149). One interesting corollary is that these two scholars have come to see this as not actually an issue, but as an imaginary exercise which builds up expectations on the basis of a biblical allusion and a subliminal reference to the Hobbesian concept of a pre-political ‘State of Nature’.

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